

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Deliverables/Milestones

Document info

Title	M2.2 TMD support for and suggestions of new assessment metrics, e.g. related to impact
Deliverable/Milestone Number	M2.2
Responsible Participant	Eleni Adamidi – Athena Research Center
WP Number	2
Dissemination level	PU

Version history

Version	Revised by	Date	Comment
0.1	Eleni Adamidi	23/11/2025	First draft
1.0.0	Eleni Adamidi, Olivier Sand, Nina Norgen, Brane Leskošek	18/12/2025	Final version

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Executive Summary

A new version of the Training Metrics Database (TMD) has been published here <https://tmd.elixir-europe.org> and now technically supports impact-oriented assessment of training activities through platform changes rather than another update of the ELIXIR core questions. The release introduces Node-specific metrics on top of ELIXIR core metrics, allowing Nodes to capture information that is relevant to their local needs, new metrics templates with backward compatibility for existing templates and updated answer options reflecting the stakeholder consultations. These developments ensure the TMD can collect, store, and present metrics in a flexible way across Nodes, while supporting both harmonised reporting and local evaluation needs over time.

Outcomes and Impacts

TMD is now technically ready for additional metrics, including:

- Node-specific question sets alongside the ELIXIR core, all versioned in TMD.
- New templates available, with backward compatibility for legacy templates.
- Updated answer options, documented in the GitHub wiki (Demographic, Quality, Impact reference pages).

Operational support is provided through issue and feature reporting via the TMD pages or the Slack channel #tmd. Step-by-step documentation on adding question sets and using the new templates can be found here: <https://github.com/elixir-europe-training/Training-Metrics-Database/wiki>.

As a result, the platform is ready for new assessment metrics across ELIXIR core and Node-specific extensions, making adoption and documentation easier for Nodes.